

Grant Agreement N°101092861

Making the Invisible Visible for Off-Highway Machinery by Conveying Extended Reality Technologies

DELIVERABLE 6.7 – PRIVACY ASSESSMENT RESULTS

Document Identification

Project THEIA^{XR}

Project Full Title	Making the Invisible Visible for Off-Highway Machinery by Conveying Extended Reality Technologies
Project Number	101092861
Starting Date	January 1st, 2023
Duration	3 years
Horizon Europe Programme	Horizon Europe Framework Program (HORIZON)
Topic	HORIZON-CL4-2022-HUMAN-01-14: “eXtended Reality Technologies”
Call for proposal	HORIZON-CL4-2022-HUMAN-01
Type of Action	RIA-Research & Innovation Action
Website	www.theia-xr.eu
Work Package	WP6
WP Leader	PRIN
Responsible Partner(s)	UL
File Name	D 6.7 – Privacy assessment results
Contractual delivery date	31.12.2025
Actual delivery date	23.12.2025
Version	1
Status	Final
Dissemination level	Public
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Internal Reviewer	Martijn Rooker, TTC Sarah Bacher, HdM

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Executive summary

The presented deliverable summarises work done in the project on the side of privacy and ethics. The results are based on procedures outlined in D2.3 (GDPR-compliance-inspired questionnaire; the fulfilment of Privacy Requirements (final version) is incorporated in D3.10) and in D3.8 (explanation of the final assessment scales and forward analysis). The Deliverable is structured as follows: First we make a brief overview of the current discussion of privacy and ethics-related parameters in XR in relation to technology development. Second, we present the results of preliminary evaluation of the perception of privacy and ethics of our solutions based on-site evaluation with end-users in the INTERALPIN Trade Fair (more information about the event can be found in D7.5), N=36. When we describe the two parts of our main evaluation: conceptual evaluation of interaction between different implementation parameters (N=264) and demonstrator-based evaluation in each use case (N=6, 3 and 10 respectively) . We finished with the described evaluation of the privacy self-assessment from the project partners. This is the final deliverable for privacy and ethics evaluation in the project.

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1 Introduction

The movement towards Industry 5.0 acknowledges human ethics and values (including privacy values) as the centre of developed technologies [3]. For example, [13] showed how ethical and human-centred frameworks for AI are shaping Industry 5.0 by discussing the requirements of Industry 5.0. and the ethical answers Human-Centred AI can provide. In the domain of industrial operations, more works show the applicability of designing for ethics and privacy principles in the domain (e.g., [9], also D3.8 for extended review on the methods). However, it is still difficult to create proper measures to evaluate the impact of these practices on the final product, e.g. have measurable outcomes of the value and privacy-inspired solutions. Specifically talking about the ethical component in industrial XR implementations, [5] pointed to the limited number of works that empirically validated the application of ethical frameworks in the industrial XR domain.

Within the framework of the THEIA^{XR} project, we tried to address these gaps by providing validated ethical parameters, which can be quantifiably measured. While the project progressed, we realised that there is a very limited number of privacy questionnaires, which can be easily adapted to the project; moreover, to the best of our knowledge, there is no existing and validated questionnaire addressing ethical considerations of the XR in a working place. Therefore, our goal in the project becomes not just to identify ethically relevant constructs but also to develop appropriate instruments to measure them. The present document contains the results of multiple procedures aimed at measuring different aspects of ethics and privacy in the domain of the development of industrial XR. Our results contain further design recommendations, which can be used by researchers and practitioners in the stage of industrial implementation of the solutions.

2 Preliminary evaluation

2.1 INTERALPIN Trade Fair UC1 evaluation

We perform an on-site evaluation during the presentation of the Snow Groomer UC1 Demonstrator. The procedure was organized as follows: we waited until the Trade Fair visitor tried the implementations in the Demonstration cabin, and when they asked them to answer a short questionnaire about the perception of the implementations. As we were in a fair context, we made our testing process as lightweight as possible so that people stay no more than 5 minutes after the cabin testing. We used a bipolar scale based on the 4-dimensional question questionnaire, based on the extended Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) dimensions presented in D3.8 (difficult to use - easy to use, useless - useful, boring - enjoyable, dangerous - safe). Additionally, we utilised the UEQ+ questionnaire (4-item Trust scale) [10] and the 3-question MUIPC version [18] (one question for each dimension). The description of the instruments could be found in D3.8. However, based on the strong feedback after the first day of evaluation, we realised that it very difficult for our participants to evaluate the privacy dimension after testing the demonstrator, as people often mention that the privacy perception will depend a) on the exact implementation, b) in a real operational company scenario, so we decided to concentrate on ethical dimensions in the following days.

We describe our demographics data as follow:

- 7 participants declared their gender as female, 27 as male, and 2 persons preferred not to disclose their gender.
- 9 participants were 18 to 25 years old, 16 participants 26 to 39 years old, 9 participants 40 to 59 years old, 1 over 60 years old and 1 prefers not to disclose their age.

- 13 participants declared no prior operation experience. 1 participant reported less than one year of experience, 3 reported one to two years, 7 reported three to five years of experience. 4 participants had more than five years of experience, 6 with more than ten years, and 2 with more than twenty years of experience.

2.1.1 Evaluation results

2.1.1.1 Technology Acceptance and perception of privacy

The results (N=36) are presented in the table. Based on the results, we can mention a considerable pattern of perceiving the technology as rather easy to use, useful, safe and enjoyable (all means are leaning towards the right sides of bipolar scales).

Table 1: Results of brief prototype evaluation in UC1

Measurement	Mean (hereafter – M)	Standard Deviation (hereafter – SD)
Perceived Ease of Use	5.47	1.28
Perceived Usefulness	5.53	1.28
Enjoyment	5.75	1.16
Safety	6.03	1.34

2.1.1.2 Trust and Privacy Concerns Scales (MUIPC short) and Trust Scale (UEQ+)

Our results on trust and privacy perception (N= 13) look as follows:

Participants have a very high level of trust in the solution: M=23.31 (with possible range from 0 to 28); SD=3.45, in contrast, the level of Privacy Concerns was rather low: M=10.92, SD =5.2 (with possible range from 3 to 21); therefore we can conclude that the solutions were perceived as trustworthy and privacy-preserving. However, as it was mentioned above, people raised concerns about applicability of any privacy measurements outside the real use of machines.

2.1.1.3 Qualitative findings

We also asked participants to summarise their experience in one or two sentences to have a brief understanding of the strong points and the potential problems with the presented solutions. The results are summarised in Figure 1. As shown, they are in line with the Ethical Workshop explorations of the operator's values (details are provided in D.3.8), therefore giving additional validation to the constructs of potential overreliance, distraction and detachment.

2.1.2 Recommendations

Based on the quantitative data and qualitative feedback, we summarise the following recommendations for future implementations and testing:

- At first glance, the system exhibits desirable properties in terms of efficiency, ease of use, perceived safety, and enjoyment of work. However, all these parameters should be verified in longitudinal testing, as e.g., enjoyment can be tied to novelty of the system [15];
- Privacy questions are not testable without relation to the organisational policies of data use; while the prototype was perceived in generally trustworthy, because it was not implied straightforward collection of data, it can become a concern in some organisational cultures.
- Some of the features can be perceived as annoying; the operators mentioned that the solutions somehow clutter the visual field. Especially for experienced operators, it is necessary to implement tangible control over features.

Figure 1: Visual summary of qualitative findings

3 Final Evaluations

3.1 Task-based evaluation in UC1, UC2 and UC3

In the frames of task-based demonstrators evaluation (described in D3.10, Section 2.4) we implemented several questionnaires oriented to grasp users' perception of privacy qualities of technology. Our sample is described as follow: UC1 evaluation contained 6 full evaluations, all participants were male, age M=38.67, SD=4.5, working experience 16.17, SD=4.24);, UC2 has 3 full evaluations, all participants were male, age M = UC3 evaluations contained 10 full evaluations, age M=31.18, SD=4.51, working experience=8.27, SD=2.93) UC was represented by 2 engineers with operational experience helping to install and test UC 2 demonstrator on Kalmar side (39, N/a).

The results of quantitative evaluation for UC1 and UC3 presented in the Table 2.

Table 2: Evaluation results of task-based tests

Scales	UC1	UC2	UC3	Described Benchmarks (as described in D2.5)	Results (KPI fulfilment)
UEQ+ TRUST	M=22.17 ,SD =3.13; M/4 = 5.54	M=23.33, SD=0.58, M/4 = 5.83	M=23.50 SD=3.03, M/4 = 5.87	M/4>=4	achieved
UEQ+ TRUSTWORTHNESS	M=21.67, SD=2.25 ;M/4 =5.48	M=27.00, SD = 1; M/4 = 6.75	M=24,50 SD=2,76, M/4 = 6.12	M/4>=4	achieved

MUIPC (whole scale)	M =25.50, SD = 11.26	M = 32.00, SD = 3.00	M=29.20, SD =11.55	no specific benchmark for whole scale	
MUIPC (perceived surveillance)	M = 7.5, SD = 3.21, M/3= 2.5	M=14.33, SD=0.58, M/3 = 4,78	M=9.80, SD=3.88, M/3 = 3.26	M/3 <=4	Mostly achieved, UC2 demonstrated elevated concerns on surveillance
MUIPC (perceived intrusion)	M = 9.5, SD = 3.67,, M/3 = 3.16	M=10.67, SD=0.58, M/3 = 3,54	M=10.00, SD=4.03, M/3 =3.33	M/3 <=4	achieved
MUIPC (data collection)	M = 8.5, SD= 4.59, M/3 = 2.84	M=7.00, SD=2.00, M/3 = 2.33	M = 9.40,SD = 4.93, M/3 = 3.13	M/3 <=4	achieved

It should be mentioned that the general privacy concerns of the participants, measured by IUIPC, were rather high (UC1 M=49.5, SD=6,16, UC2 M=46.00, SD=4.36, UC3 M= 45.00, SD=5.21), compared to a possible range from 8 to 56 and previous work, M = 49 as a high level of concern [1]. The results indicate that participants in our sample are generally privacy-aware; that provide additional evidence of the positive privacy qualities of our solutions (even privacy-aware people find them as privacy-preserving). The elevated numbers in perceived surveillance from the solutions in UC2 probably related to the multi-cameras setup and can be mitigated by the applying strict rules to the observations.

3.1.1 Recommendations

- The evaluation demonstrated that, in general, prototypes do not raise significant privacy concerns; therefore, the current version of technologies can be recommended for further tests in industrial applications.
- At the same time, the implementations should be supported by a) clear organisational policies explaining use of data (which data are collected, which stored and how the stored data can be used) b) educational program to the operators, which explain the limit of applicability of the features, the way features are interacting with operational process, and protocol of human verification of the features information.

3.1.2 Additional qualitative evaluation in UC2

As the sample size of quantitative measurements in UC2 was very low, we decided to compliment it by conducting additional qualitative evaluations on the perception of this demonstrator. The UC2 leads (Kalmar), together with VTT, performed an evaluation of integrated technologies in UC2. After the evaluations, we conducted interviews with all (2) engineers (both male, one of whom was 39 years old and another did not provide the information), involved in the installation and testing of the technology.

For this purpose we created a guide for a semi-structured interview, presented below:

General Questions: ¹

- How many years have you been working with reach stackers/other distant operation devices?

¹ We acknowledge the use of Claude AI to refine and debiasing some of the questions. No partners information was inserted into the AI system.

- Have already being involved in other projects that includes XR and distant operation elements? If yes, can you briefly explain the functionality you have tested/used (please don't the question if these things are under NDA)

Testing:

- Can you tell us more about the testing? Can you briefly explain what did you test?
- What was your general impressions?
- How did that go?
- What difficulty did you have?
- Just to summarize, what did you like? What did you like less?
- Any suggestions for improvement?

Security/Privacy/Safety:

- What about security?
- How did you perceive security while operating the prototype?
- Let's imagine the prototype is used in real operations by real operators. What risks could be where?
- In which context/ situation on privacy and data gathering did the system collect any information during operation?
- What kind of data was collected?
- Can you list them?
- Could you think of other types of data that would be relevant or useful to collect in operating the machine?
- How do you feel about the privacy of the data collected?
- Can you think of any possible risks or concerns related to this data collection?

Agency and Independence:

- What about freedom of action?
- Did you perceive control over the system, or did you feel that the system guided your actions?
- In the end, do you think it gives workers more control or less control?

Presence/detachment from work, over automation, and enjoyment from the work:

- How do you think it might change the way operators work?
- Any benefits or drawbacks you can think of?
- Do you think this implementation will make the job more or less enjoyable?
- Do you think the implementation will make the job more or less interesting?
- What about the feeling of presence? Did you feel the same presence on the job as you do on the real machine?
- In our previous interviews, the participants raised concerns that the implementation of the XR features in a distant operation scenario will make the job too much resemble a computer game. What is your opinion about that? In real operation, do you experience a similar feeling, or is your experience completely different?

Closing remarks:

- Any other comments?
- Questions?

3.1.3 Key findings from the interviews

3.1.3.1 Problems with safety, visibility, and visual distraction in the implementations

Both participants mentioned that the machine itself creates serious concerns for safety; in this sense, the demonstrator addresses only part of the problem, e.g., not helping to improve safety in the rear of the machine. This zone is particularly problematic, especially if the machine is doing a backward movement, as the visibility is very low. In combination with the containers' counterweight, it creates a serious risk of

crushing; future prototypes should address this problem and give more support to the blind zones. Similarly, a person detection system should mount an area around the vehicle, not only in front of the vehicle. The participants mentioned that a multicamera solution (cameras around the operation space) with a real-time switch is a good solution for the problem, and both participants hope for more advanced integration of it into the vehicle monitoring. Both participants criticise the greed-based container position system as a) too complex for interpretation, b) too distracting and cluttering. They mentioned that the current system actually increases the cognitive load and makes the operation more complex, therefore, visual representation would be simplified, like a couple of dots or very simple bars to show the maximum load. Also, the system should be flexible to show only the information that the operator needs at the moment and hide other information. The usual interaction between the operator and the system is extremely fast, so the excessive information will inevitably be lost.

3.1.3.1.1 Recommendations

- Simplify visual representation.
- Provide in-context help, not all time/all information;
- Update the solutions for covering the rear part for safe movement and obstacle detection;

3.1.3.2 *Over reliance and level of experience*

Participant 1 expressed concerns about the potential impact of designed features on security. If operators do not check the things shown by the guiding system, it will lead to problems in the operation. Both participants think that the features will be quite useful for the beginners (and in this respect - less useful for experienced operators), however there is a risk that the relying on the features will substitute the operator's critical thinking. If operators will not check the things, showed by the guiding system, it will lead to problems in the operation. Participant 2 mentioned that it is very important to be able to turn the features on and off and adapt the features to the operating level.

3.1.3.2.1 Recommendations

- Provide the opportunity to adapt system's functions to operator's needs;
- Pay attention to how the non-experienced operator uses the system, possibly limiting access to the system while learning;
- Implement a verification protocol while operating, the operator should be prompted to always check themselves.

3.1.3.3 *Remote operations risks*

Participant 1 expressed serious doubts about remote operations in the domain. First, it can make work less pleasant, as for many people, working outside in fresh air has a different feeling than working in front of a distant screen. It simultaneously makes the work more boring, repetitive, and less real. Participants mentioned that loosening the grip on reality can affect the operator's attention to the operation and provoke errors. In addition, participants shared technical concerns about distant operation - even a short loss of connection with the vehicle can create an incident. The camera view can also be something that triggers mistakes, as it does not have the depth and details of the real view from the real cabin. As a potential solution, participants proposed the shift work, where operators have some shifts in real machine and some in distant operations to keep the feeling of the working process.

3.1.3.3.1 Recommendations

- Apply the shifts model for operation, alternate real and distant operations
- Test the feasibility of distant operations, provide defence mechanisms against situations where the connection is lost.

3.1.3.4 Data privacy and experience with data

Both participants mentioned that data collection in the workplace is omnipresent, and therefore, the solution does not create any additional risks. The participants vary in their level of concern about the extra data, and they use it, e.g. for evaluation and internal competition, which can trigger unsafe behaviour, but on the other hand, if the features can be helpful for business, the industry can decide to opt for more collection. Anyway, as mentioned, the main driver in the industry is safety, so the business will approve any data collection oriented towards safety.

3.1.3.4.1 Recommendation

- Verify data usage with end users and organizational stakeholders to find a sweet spot where concerns about data usage from workers meet productivity and safety expectations from the companies.

3.2 Large-scale Privacy and Ethics Parameters Evaluation (UC1, UC2, UC3)

To understand the privacy and ethics perception of project technologies on a diverse and larger sample of the operators, we conducted an online panel-based vignette experiment (the participants assess short, hypothetical scenarios (in our case - XR features implementations) in which we vary key details; that allows us to measure how those differences influence perception of our solutions. More details of the method presented in [2].) We invited operators to participate in the evaluation of our technologies. We took visual prototypes with a detailed description which reflected the technologies implemented in 3 use cases: Guiding lines in the operation area (both snow grooming and potentially excavating scenarios UC1 + UC3), Ambient lights in proximity warnings/obstacle detection scenario (UC1 + UC3) and twist lock support grid (UC2). We choose these technologies

for the following reasons: a) they can be understood by description and schematic image, while, for example, it would be difficult to do for haptic technologies; b) these technologies were implemented in different stages of demonstrators; c) they provoke the most discussion in the sessions with operators. All three designs were implemented in the semi-experimental vignettes-based design [2], **resulting in 3 vignettes** where we vary the following parameters:

- **Collection mode:** described technology either collected data for the operation and when discarded (condition 1) OR collected data and stored it under the operator's ID (condition 2)
- **Opportunity to enable/disable feature:** the operator could switch the XR system in any moment (1) or the system was always active (2)
- **System reminders about the independence of the operation:** XR system either reminded the operator to verify the operation conditions themselves (1) or did not do that (2)
- **Communication:** XR system either did not affect the working communication (1) or reduced the communication (2). The example of a vignette presented in Figure 2

Figure 2: Experimental condition, the picture represents the demonstrator design based on information scenarios and contextual inquiries

For the evaluation we used the ethics and privacy questionnaire, as well as short form of Technology Acceptance Model by [4], Online Privacy Concerns Scale by Masur [12] and ME-Work scale [16] (The questionnaires are described in D3.8). We implemented D-efficient vignette design, as it demonstrated higher psychometric properties compared to random sampling from vignette space, while still reducing the burden on sample size [17]. In the final design, each participant evaluates 1 of 8 possible vignette conditions for all three different technology-related vignettes.

Following EU Open Science Policy [8], the study's sample size, hypotheses and measurements were preregistered: <https://aspredicted.org/p4vm97.pdf>. We also make our dataset publicly available after the project is completed.

3.2.1 Results of the evaluation

3.2.1.1 Data Collection and Descriptive Statistics

We collected our data on the Prolific² research panel platform. We first specify the industries, where the operator could work (e.g. Construction, Logistics, Heavy Machinery), and when distributed a pre-screening questionnaire for this population. In the results, we received applications from near 400 people claiming to have operational experience. When we sent the invitation to the main study procedure to this specific population, we were able to collect 303 responses. After deleting the participants who failed the comprehension check at least twice (which means that participants did not understand how the different parameters were presented in the final prototype), we received 264 answers.

² <https://www.prolific.com>

The sample has following characteristics: 183 self-declared as male, 79 as female and 2 prefer not to disclose the information, M age was 36.69, SD = 11.89, M declared experience with one of Off-Highway Machinery-related industrial domains (e.g., Forestry, Construction) is 8.16, SD = 7.66, and M professional experience as operator is 4.79 (conservative estimates, as some participants with less than a year experience posted 0 in the form). The 186 participants reported experience with excavators, 91 with reach stackers, and 36 with snow groomers. In addition, 17 participants mentioned experience with Forklift/Lift Trucks, 12 - with tractors and farm equipment, and 7 - with loaders. 7 with other construction site equipment, 5 - trucks and haulers and 2 - with material handlers (sum is bigger than 264 as some people declared multiple experiences).

3.2.1.2 Main results

We merge the results of the evaluation of 3 vignettes into a single dataset. For the hypothesis testing we applied Generalized Linear Models [7] with robustness adjustment on repeated measures [11] and ME-Work and Online Privacy Concerns scale as covariates [6]. The results of testing the main hypotheses with short interpretations presented in the Table 3:

Table 3: Results of experiment-based evaluation of implemented features on perception of ethical and privacy dimensions

Hypothesis	Statistics	Status	Interpretation
Main effects, manipulation checks			
Data storage of the operations increases concerns about data collection.	Collection concerns are significantly higher in the storing condition ($p < .001$)	confirmed	The mere fact of storing the operation's information significantly raises the level of associated concerns.
Inability to switch the system on and off significantly lowers the perception of the operation's autonomy.	Perception of autonomy at work is significantly higher in the condition where the system allows switching it on and off ($p < .001$).	confirmed	A system that is always active by design reduces users' sense of freedom in operations.
The system, which asks users to verify information, is perceived as raising critical thinking about operations.	The system, which does not ask users to verify information, is perceived as better for raising critical thinking ($p < .001$)	not confirmed, strong effect in opposite direction	A system that asks users to verify its decisions is perceived as annoying and as diminishing thinking
The systems, which diminish communication and interaction, also diminish the sense of collaboration.	The system, which diminishes interaction and communication, is perceived as worsening collaboration ($p < .001$);	confirmed	Operators perceive a strong relationship between collaborative efforts and patterns of communication and interaction.
Effects on acceptance of our solutions			
Privacy-preserving systems are perceived as more acceptable.	The system that does not collect operational data is more acceptable ($p = .002$)	confirmed	If the system does not store collected data, it is perceived as more acceptable.
A system that allows users to switch it on and off is more acceptable.	The system that gives users the opportunity to switch it on and off is perceived as more acceptable ($p < .001$)	confirmed	If the system can be switched on and off by the operator, it is more acceptable, a finding also

			confirmed in qualitative interviews.
A system that prompts users to verify and check is more acceptable.	We did not find evidence that either the system that prompts users to check or the system that does not is more acceptable ($p = .398$).	not confirmed	Prompting operators to check is probably a double-edged sword, with some people perceiving it as a positive factor and others as a negative one. More studies are needed to understand its effect.
A system that preserves workplace communication is more acceptable.	A system that preserves workplace communication and interactions is perceived as more acceptable ($p = .002$),	confirmed	Operators still prefer systems that maintain the status quo in workplace communication, (that likely reflecting their understanding of human contact and working relationships in the workplace).
Effects on additional ethical dimensions			
Restriction of autonomy increases the sense of distraction.	We did not find evidence that autonomy restriction (a system that is always on) contributes to the sense of distraction ($p = .349$).	not confirmed	The always-on feature is probably annoying to autonomy but is not necessarily perceived as a source of distraction.
A system that always asks for verification and the operator's decision-making is perceived as more distracting.	We did not find evidences that systematically asking for verification create sense of distraction ($p=.695$)	not confirmed	Asking for verification is probably not perceived as a particularly distracting feature.
Restriction of autonomy prompts a sense of boredom.	We found evidence that restriction of autonomy significantly increases the sense of boredom from operations ($p = .005$); neither meaningful work nor privacy concerns affect these interactions.	confirmed	A system that reduces the operator's freedom in controlling the vehicle is perceived as provoking boredom at work..
Effect of interactions between different ethics- and privacy-related parameters			
The interaction between reduced communication and a non-switchable system creates a sense of skill devaluation.	We did not find a significant interaction effect between the parameters ($p = .188$); however, we found a significant negative effect of reduced communication on skill devaluation ($p = .012$).	not confirmed	The combination of the two dehumanization factors did not affect the perception of a loss of work value due to technology. In contrast, the positive effect of reduced communication on the sense of job value showed that operators believe that being less dependent on others' work demonstrates that

			their skills remain valuable.
Restriction of communication and autonomy makes the job even more boring.	While both autonomy restriction ($p = .027$) and communication restriction ($p < .001$) are significant independent predictors of boredom, we did not find any interaction effect between them.	not confirmed	Autonomy restriction and communication restriction probably induce different types of boredom.
Effects of differences between presented technologies			
Vignette 3 (twist-lock positioning) creates a more intense sense of detachment compared to the other conditions.	The results show a significant effect in the opposite direction: Vignette 3 is perceived as providing significantly less sense of detachment ($p < .016$). comparing to Vignette 2 (Ambient lights)	not confirmed	As the vignette description is not specifically tied to teleoperation, this vignette with a multicamera setup was probably perceived as supporting a sense of reality.
Vignette 2 (Ambient lights) creates a more intense sense of distraction compared to the other conditions.	The results show that Vignette 3 is perceived as more distracting compared to Vignette 1 ($p < .004$).	not confirmed	This reflects the UC2 evaluation participants' perspective on visual grids as an extremely distracting feature (see Chapter 2.2 for reference).

In addition, we evaluated general Acceptance and Technological Acceptance of each solution regardless of ethics and privacy controls configurations to see the effects of the exact designs of solutions. The results are presented in Table 4.

Table 4: Results of general acceptance of technology

Technology		Acceptability	Interpretation	TAM questionnaire	Interpretation
Ground lines (protection of the operation area)	M	14.85	Very high acceptance (as measured in a scale from 0 to 20)	65.83	High acceptance (as measured by scale from 12 to 84)
	SD	4.331		11.881	
Ambient lights for obstacle detection/collision avoidance	M	15.94	Very high acceptance (as measured in a scale from 0 to 20)	67.50	High acceptance (as measured by scale from 12 to 84)
	SD	4.292		11.417	
Grids for supporting container handling	M	14.94	Very high acceptance (as measured in a scale from 0 to 20)	65.63	High acceptance (as measured by scale from 12 to 84)
	SD	4.403		11.981	
Total	M	15.25		66.32	
	SD	4.365		11.776	

Finally, to fulfill the KPI on privacy on a similar manner as we did in the on-sight test, we specifically measured privacy concerns in the non-collection conditions (as stated in our final implementation), but also in the storing condition. We did both evaluations because the companies probably would like to implement this

version in the future. We applied the same criterium: concerns should not be higher than middle point (4 on 7 points Likert scale). Because in the online version we used a 4-question structure for the Privacy Collection Scale, we applied the following formula $M/4 \leq 4$; the results are presented in Table 5:

Table 5: Fulfilment of requirement towards collection-based privacy concerns

Condition	M(SD)	M/4	Fulfilment status (KPI 4.1)
Guiding lines in the operation area(collection, no storage)	9.51 (5.87)	2.37	fulfilled
Guiding lines in the operation area (collection and storage)	13.62 (7.08)	3.41	fulfilled
Twist lock and container positioning supporting grid (collection, no storage)	9.88 (5.99)	2.47	fulfilled
Twist lock and container positioning supporting grid (collection, no storage)	13.51	3.38	fulfilled
Ambient lights in collision avoidance (collection, no storage)	9.92 (5.92)	2.48	fulfilled
Ambient lights in collision avoidance (collection, no storage) (collection and storage)	13.60 (7.07)	3.40	fulfilled

As the results show, the privacy-preserving non-storing mode is still preferable in the technology implementation; however, even in the situation where operational data are collected and stored, operators still accept it as privacy-tolerable.

3.2.2 Recommendations

- Prioritize solutions, which minimize storage of the data (collection and in-shift use are not creating any concerns);
- Designers should pay attention to the way of implementing critical thinking cues into the operational process, as regular checkup requests can be perceived as annoying and patronising; at the same time, not implementing the features can create in-presence overreliance risks;
- Designers should avoid implementing guiding features in always-on mode, as they can increase perceived boredom of operations and create disruptive long-term effects;
- Designers should avoid solutions which substitute communication processes integrated in the job. While operators mentioned that their job is usually more individualistic, solutions, diminishing communication also increase boredom.

3.3 Stakeholders self-evaluation privacy risks in the project

To assess the stakeholders' perception of privacy risks of the finalised technologies, we asked stakeholders to evaluate the final state of privacy in the project solutions, using the form described in D2.3. We received 10 forms (one from the representatives of technology and stakeholders providers in the project). First, we analysed the Consortium consensus on privacy risks of the projects, second, we discussed the perceived risks of particular technological solutions and system and provide recommendations how they should be mitigated in the final project (each partner provided evaluation of the risks, associated with their technologies). Results are presented in Table 6.

Table 6: Self-assessment of privacy risks in the project

Partner	Evaluation or scoring, including profiling and predicting	Automated decision making with significant effect:	Systematic monitoring:	Sensitive data or data of a highly personal nature	Data processed on a large scale	Matching or combining datasets,	Data concerning vulnerable data subjects	Innovative use or applying new technologies	Mean Score per Partner
CREA	5	2	3	3	1	1	1	4	2,5
HAP	1	2	1	1	1	1	1	2	1,25
TTC	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
VTT	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
KAL	2	1	1	1	2	1	1	5	1,75
HdM	2	1	1	1	1	1	1	5	1,625
TUD	2	4	2	1	1	3	2	3	2,25
UL	2	1	2	1	1	1	1	3	1,5
TUG	1	1	1	1	2	1	1	5	1,625
PRIN	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
Mean Score per Risk	1,8	1,5	1,4	1,2	1,2	1,2	1,1	3	

The results show low risks of our outcomes both per partner and per group of risks, which reflect the final set of technologies selected for the project. Slightly higher than average risk, dedicated to innovative use of technologies is inevitable in the technological project, and does not mean a decline from the privacy goals. We also asked partners to evaluate their technologies on the level of potential risks and the ways in which risks are represented in the project. The partners mentioned low levels of potential risks in the project; the only part related to more extended data collection and elevated risks were related to simulator use while prototyping technologies. These risks were mitigated by in-device processing of data handling procedures.

3.3.1 Recommendations

- The project followed a privacy-by-design approach and did not create any significant privacy risks. However, as we acknowledge the innovative use of technologies, it is possible that future use of technology poses additional privacy risks. In the project, we applied procedures of Humanity-Centred [14] and Z-inspection [19] workshops to reflect on the current data gathering situation and specify the action plan on emerging risks; when the project’s technology moves from research to commercial use, the risks should be reevaluated to include the context of real use.

4 Conclusions

Our result shows that while different implementations of "controllers" for privacy and ethics in realistic operation scenarios can significantly affect acceptance, the operators have positive privacy- and ethics-perception of developed technologies. However, it is essential to ensure that while guiding operators to critically think about the situation, we do not overburden them with excessive guidance (both in visual presentations and system requests), as this can be perceived as an intrusion into their workflow. The findings contribute to a better understanding of XR technologies implemented in the working process and raise the state of the art about understanding how privacy and ethics should be embedded in exact technological scenarios.

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ABBREVIATIONS / ACRONYMS

[XR]	Extended Reality
[M]	Mean
[SD]	Standard Deviation